

PSDI

PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

PSDI DCC Community Workshop Report: Edinburgh and Southampton 2024

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1 Summary

What We Did

The Digital Curation Centre (DCC) partnered with the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI) to conduct two community workshops in the summer of 2024: one in Edinburgh, Scotland, and one in Southampton, England. The goal was to directly engage with researchers and other stakeholders in physical sciences to better understand the current challenges and opportunities around data sharing, as well as to gather requirements for the PSDI platform to facilitate such data sharing and a cross-discipline, cross-sector collaboration more broadly.

What We Found

Main challenges to data sharing and reuse in physical sciences:

Note: Sharing research data with project collaborators during the project is more established than sharing (or publishing) the data more broadly and presents different challenges.

- Researchers may want to share their data - but lack knowledge and support.
- In the absence of established disciplinary standards, documentation (including metadata) is a challenge. In contrast to software developers, scientists lack the skills and habits to sufficiently document their process and outputs to make them reproducible. Computational tools create automatic logs but more conceptual information still needs to be added manually.
- Compliance with the funding, academic publishing, and institutional requirements remains a key driver of data sharing. This applies to data management plans as well.
- The cost (in time and resources) of data management and curation is another barrier to data sharing. Large datasets and proprietary file formats aggravate the issues.
- A culture of selective data is the norm. Incomplete or imperfect data is not shared to avoid reputational damage. Conversely, high-quality data is not shared for fear of losing the competitive advantage in funding or publication.
- Data reuse is still perceived as lesser than collecting or generating your own data.

What We Recommend

How PSDI can help address the challenges and gaps in support in physical sciences:

Recommendation 1: An integrated PSDI platform for data collection, storage, analysis, aggregation, and curation would help solve many technical problems and help establish and implement much needed standards and best practices in physical sciences research, while putting data sharing and open collaboration at the centre.

- Eliminate pain points to move the field toward “frictionless” data workflows.
- Standards and guidance on data management, data sharing, and documentation.
- At-the-point-of-need support as well as consultancy and bespoke solutions.
- Pilot and guide the responsible use of AI in physical sciences research.

Recommendation 2: In addition to providing an integrated technical solution, the PSDI platform could become a one-stop hub of up-to-date disciplinary knowledge, training, resources, and tools, as well as a community-building hub in physical sciences.

- A trusted provider and curator of online and in-person training.
- A community hub to foster trust, collaboration, and knowledge exchange.
- Funded fellowship for trainees and grants to develop specific outputs.

2 Background and Context

Overview of the PSDI Project

Data needs in research are growing at previously unimaginable rates and the need for collaboration around data has never been clearer. However, in the Physical Sciences, many research bodies, from large facility to laboratory, have their own data infrastructure with limited ability to share, integrate and reuse data across systems.

Funded by the UK Research and Innovation: Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (UKRI-EP SRC), the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI, www.psd.ac.uk/) Project aims to provide a data infrastructure that connects existing experimental and computational facilities within Physical Sciences and thus add value and accelerate research in Physical Science disciplines in the United Kingdom.

In the longer term, the PSDI aims to enable:

- A platform for data collection, sharing, aggregation, integration and curation.
- Supporting analysis across experimental simulation and reference data.
- Combining and enhancing existing data infrastructures.
- Sustaining data resources beyond the lifespan of individual research projects.

3 Community Workshop Methodology

The goal of each workshop was to directly engage with researchers in physical sciences as well as other stakeholders in academic research, government, and industry, in order to better understand the current barriers, challenges, opportunities, and solutions around data sharing, as well as to gather requirements for the PSDI platform to more effectively facilitate and advance such data sharing and a cross-discipline, cross-sector collaboration more broadly.

Toward that goal, each workshop started with an overview of the PSDI Project and its goals and also included dedicated time for networking and conversation between the participants.

During the workshop proper, the DCC team used a facilitated-workshop approach and semi-structured questions to gather information and insights from the stakeholders (a methodology similar to focus groups). The workshops were held in person in a room set up for group work. Participants were divided into small groups of 5-6 people per table, with one facilitator and note-taker at each table.

To ease the pressure on the facilitators to take notes while simultaneously leading the discussion, and to ensure that a complete and accurate record of the conversation was captured, participants were also provided with printed worksheets to write on during the workshop and invited to contribute to a shared digital document after the event.

Two in-person, half-day community workshops were conducted in the summer of 2024: one in Edinburgh, Scotland, and one in Southampton, England. The target audience for both workshops was anyone working with research data in the Physical Sciences, including data stewards, early-career and senior researchers, and research support staff, as well as industry representatives. The workshops were promoted via professional connections, community email lists, and social media platforms such as LinkedIn. Registration was conducted via an online form and was free.

Edinburgh Workshop: July 24th, 2024

The Edinburgh community workshop took place on July 24th, 2024, in the Charteris Land Building in Edinburgh. While the number of participants was relatively small (16 people total, including the PSDI and DCC), academic research, research services, and industry were represented. Participants included faculty and/or staff from the University of Edinburgh, Glasgow University, Aberdeen University, and Heriot-Watt University.

The workshop kicked off with coffee and networking, followed by a short presentation to introduce the PSDI Project. Most of the time was spent in moderated small-group discussions, which were followed by a short break and a feedback activity. The workshop concluded with a wrap-up and information on how to get involved with the PSDI. See the workshop agenda in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Edinburgh workshop agenda.

Time	Activity
13:45	Coffee and networking
14:15	Introduction to PSDI
14:45	Moderated small-group discussions
	Break
16:05	Feedback activity
16:25	Wrap up and how to get involved

Southampton Workshop: August 8th, 2024

The Southampton Workshop took place on August 8th, 2024, in the Sir James Matthews Building in Southampton. While the number of participants was relatively small again (16 people, including the PSDI and DCC), academic research, research services, and industry were again represented. Participants included faculty and/or staff from the University of Southampton, University of Warwick, and Imperial College of London.

The Southampton workshop kicked off with coffee and welcome, followed by introduction to the PSDI Project. Most of the time was again spent in moderated small-group discussions, then lunch and networking time, followed by feedback and broader discussion. The workshop concluded with a wrap-up and next steps, including information on how to get involved with the PSDI. See the workshop agenda in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Southampton workshop agenda.

Time	Activity
10:15	Coffee and welcome
10:30	Introduction to PSDI
11:00	Moderated small-group discussions

12:30	Lunch and networking
13:30	Feedback and discussion
14:15	Wrap up and next steps
15:00	End of workshop

Discussion Questions

For both workshops, the main discussion questions were as follows:

1. How is data shared and reused in the physical sciences and what challenges do people face when doing so?
2. What are the challenges in managing and sharing research data in the physical sciences and how can PSDI help address them?
3. How do you seek support around research data management and sharing in the physical sciences and are there any gaps in the available support that PSDI can help address?

Additional discussion questions:

1. How can PSDI help you to skill up for different roles, including educating leaders?
2. How do you engage with your community, and how could PSDI engage as well to better understand your needs, challenges, and opportunities?
3. Should PSDI define principles around open research and ethics – especially around data deposition and data citation?
4. What kinds of events can PSDI run to engage with the technical specialist and research support communities?
5. How should PSDI deliver knowledge in the most effective form for our audience?
6. How can PSDI ensure that content producers are able to gain appropriate recognition for contributions to PSDI, for example should PSDI mint DOIs for articles so that they can be cited, and the authors can receive credit?

4 Current Practices and Challenges in Data Sharing and Reuse in Physical Sciences

The sections below summarize the insights, observations, and suggestions gathered from the discussions during the Edinburgh and Southampton Workshops, respectively.

Edinburgh Workshop

The main sentiment among the participants was that **researchers want to share their data**, there is a will to do it and an appreciation of why it is important to the field – **but lack of knowledge and lack of support are serious barriers**.

These barriers may be particularly acute around certain steps in the process or with regard to specific types of data. For instance, insufficient knowledge of metadata and technical challenges around file formats are two barriers that may hinder data sharing. Privacy considerations around biomedical data are

another challenge. In some cases, not knowing where to start may be a barrier as well. A researcher may be afraid of doing it wrong, which could have negative consequences, so they decide not to do it at all, to avoid risks.

Lack of standardization and lack of clarity about the process can also discourage researchers from sharing their data. There is a need for concrete advice and detailed steps, rather than general guidelines which may assume a lot of knowledge and be hard to interpret.

Similarly, a **negative initial experience with support services** at their institution may hinder the researcher from seeking help from them in the future, e.g., “support staff asking questions she is not ready to answer” and “too much technical information asked in the planning phase, which is off putting.”

The requirements of publishing academic articles remain a driver of data sharing, in both positive and negative ways. The culture of academic research still revolves around published papers. There is a lot of pressure to publish, and the number of publications that a researcher produces, together with the prestige of the journals in which they are published, are important factors in securing research jobs, promotions, and funding. This leads to a focus on getting the required number and quality of publications, and may distract or discourage from data sharing, since publication of data or other research outputs is not incentivized in the same way. On the other hand, if academic publishers require data sharing as a condition of publication, this serves as a strong driver for researchers to share their data.

Institutional support for data sharing, including to meet publishers’ requirements, also plays a role. Many universities host their own data repositories and offer support around the data deposit process. One example is Edinburgh DataShare at The University of Edinburgh (datashare.ed.ac.uk). The librarians offer support for researchers who want to add their research data to the repository, including a “cheat sheet” with the minimum metadata required to get the data accepted.

Participants also commented on the persistent **negative bias around data reuse**. In some fields, reuse of someone else’s data in their research is still seen as lesser than collecting or generating their own data.

This bias might stem in part from one’s research experience being limited to experimental research as opposed to more theoretical or computational research. One participant reflected on making the transition from experimental to computational methods, and their realization of “how much you can accomplish in one day when doing computational research compared to experimental research, a huge amount.”

On the other hand, **doing computational research also means a greater need for support**, including having another researcher or research assistant “standing by you to take notes on everything you do, because it’s so fast.” The fast pace of computational research means that “it is not possible to document everything at the end of the day as you did in experimental research;” but rather, the record keeping must happen in parallel with the research activities and ideally be automated in some way. Indeed, computational research uses sophisticated tools that can create a record of inputs and tasks, including logs and partial logs of activity, which reflects everything a researcher did. But one important exception, not captured in the **automatic logs**, is the more conceptual information about the research, such as the intent behind a specific step, the reason to use a certain variable, etc. This still requires human record keeping. Could researchers feasibly annotate these automatic logs and add notes on the steps, despite the speed of the process (e.g., the reason why the step was done)?

A related issue is **the need to openly share research code** as well as data and other research outputs. This code is an important part of scientific record and may provide crucial information about the research. The code may also be necessary to evaluate the quality of the research and help interpret the results. For instance, if you are a peer reviewer, “you need to look at code to be a referee on a paper submitted for publication, because the paper and all the graphs will look great, but there may be a fatal flaw.”

One participant phrased it this way: **we need “a source of truth for schemas and workflows.”** Research teams are creating something new for each project, instead of sharing with each other and reusing existing solutions and processes. One reason is how difficult it is to find out if other teams are doing the same or what they are doing. There is no place to search for this information. In some cases, there may not be a suitable place to put the research data either, especially if the data or projects are cross-disciplinary. It would also be useful to know what is coming along from other teams and the community in general.

Reproducibility is important but difficult to achieve. One participant commented that, as a field, “we want to be able to work in the way industry does,” in terms of being able to reproduce the results. But reproducibility is hard to achieve without complete datasets and full documentations being shared. This is especially urgent for critical societal challenges like climate change, where our understanding of the problems and our work toward solutions relies on interdisciplinary research and open sharing of data.

At the technical level, **proprietary software and file formats are a barrier.** You may find datasets you want to reuse, but the files are in a proprietary format, and you can only open them with proprietary software. One example of this is medical imaging, e.g. PET scans, where proprietary software and file formats are, unfortunately, the cultural norm and there is no motivation for manufacturers to change; because of the limited file formats, there is no or little data sharing possible. A good contrast is the field of crystallography. In crystallography, there is very high expectation to share all your data, and that culture of sharing creates a strong impetus to make the file formats and software more open. So cultural norms and expectations in a specific research area can spur the change toward more open, more interoperable tools and processes.

Returning to the topic of research code: in some cases, **a researcher may develop very good code, but deliberately publish only the results, not the code itself.** Their hope is that other researchers will contact them and ask to use the code, and in return, the code creator will get authorship on additional publications from other research teams. A very strategic and transactional decision that reflects the reality of academic research culture, in which publications are still much more valuable and more highly rewarded than sharing openly.

More generally, **sharing data (and other research outputs) is still perceived as risky.** Some risks come from the possibility that your data or code have errors, and by sharing them openly, you will **expose errors before they can be corrected**, and your professional reputation will suffer. This fear may be particularly relevant for interim calculations or analyses. Researchers may feel more comfortable sharing their final calculations or analyses, but not the interim ones leading to the final ones, for fear that “they are not very good.” This is also a reason not to share work in progress but only the final, polished products.

Another type of risk around sharing your data or code has to do with **giving your competitors the tools and information to outcompete or “scoop” you.** This fear is also related to the pressure to publish, and the need to protect one’s publications and to ensure that all the research culminates in a published paper, preferably in a prestigious journal. Sharing your research outputs is secondary in importance to getting the paper published.

One participant remarked: “Weird, small, imperfect projects are actually really valuable for understanding the challenges and overcoming problems.”

The participants also expressed concerns about the **sustainability of data repositories.**

Finally, there was uncertainty about **what happens when a researcher moves from one institution to another.** If you use an institutional repository, the data will remain there after you leave the institution, but will you have the same access to it? A participant also brought up **science CVs (Scientia Vita) in**

Portugal. In Portugal, all researchers have those science CVs, so when they apply for funding, they don't have to submit it, their science CV is already in the system. They can update it and add experiences like teaching and mentoring. Anyone collaborating with a Portuguese researcher can use it as well. PURE and ORCID were mentioned as similar but not identical services available in the UK.

Southampton Workshop

With respect to data sharing culture and challenges to data sharing in physical sciences, the participants made an important distinction between **sharing data with project collaborators during the project** vs. **sharing data more broadly or with other researchers, typically at the end of the project** (also sometimes referred to as **data publication**). In that way, the term *data sharing* might be ambiguous. Clearly, sharing research data with your project collaborators is much more established and generally accepted than sharing the same data more broadly; it also has different drivers and incentives as well as different risks. In addition, some of the challenges apply to both types of data sharing; other challenges may be unique to one type.

Most of the comments below pertain to data sharing outside of the project (or data publication) rather than data sharing with project collaborators, unless otherwise noted.

In general terms, the participants reported a **culture of selective data sharing** in physical sciences. Data sharing is happening to some extent, but not as much as it should. For instance, **incomplete or imperfect data is typically not shared, to avoid revealing errors** or other issues that might reflect badly on the project authors. Similarly, data leading to negative results is not shared; and such results may not be publishable, which may be one of the reasons to not share the data either. On the other hand, **high-quality data leading to strong results may not be shared for fear of losing the competitive advantage** over other research teams; this also points to a larger cultural reality of high competition for funding and publication in physical sciences.

Here, the participants acknowledged that a solution may require a **cultural change**. More specifically, there needs to be a shift towards a culture of documenting the whole research process (including negative results) and sharing incomplete work (similar to what is done in software development).

The participants were also in agreement that **compliance with requirements, or "ticking the box," is often the main motivation for sharing data**. These could be funding requirements or institutional requirements.

Another reason is publication. Sharing data falls under "doing what is needed to get published." This might mean doing only the required minimum. For instance, data management plans (DMPs) are not required by publishers, so there may be less incentive to do them.

On the other, **one barrier to data sharing is resistance to change** combined with a **frustration over being given too many tasks to do**, often halfway through the project. Some of these tasks can be perceived as interruption to the research rather than bringing value to the project. (Guidance and a process to follow from the start of the project might help here.)

Attitudes to data sharing are also influenced by **whether researchers think their data will actually be reused by others**. This is a complicated question and not easily answered. Raising awareness about all types of data reuse might help, together with real life examples and their impact.

One considerable challenge to data sharing is **documentation**. As the complexity of datasets and databases is increasing, so is the complexity of the necessary documentation. This includes metadata, ontologies, controlled vocabularies, but also project notes and other contents of research notebooks. The challenge affects more than data sharing. In some ways, researchers are the first users of their own data,

software, and documentation, and they need to understand their notes in 6 months or to pass them on to the team when they leave the project. Careful, accurate documentation is crucial during the project, for the use of the project team, as much as for the sharing and reuse afterwards. Everything should be properly documented and explained, but that is difficult and time-consuming to do and does not always happen.

Metadata is another challenge. For instance, researchers may be unsure about what metadata is needed and may not understand the benefits of rich metadata. Without clear standards or guidelines, the default behaviour might be to include as little metadata as possible, which limits both findability and reuse later on. Understanding domain content and identifying metadata to describe the data is also hard. Researchers may use “sample 1” and “sample 2” instead of the actual chemical names.

Similarly, **ontologies and controlled vocabularies** are challenging for researchers. Many ontologies are available, but they are hard to find. Metadata ontologies and vocabularies are also complicated. What looks like valid terms to use do not fit when you progress up the hierarchy and it is very difficult to make different ontologies work together effectively. The ontology lookup service is useful, but nothing exists for some domains and terms that would be useful are missing. Researchers struggle to agree on common terms and creating your own ontology becomes a massive undertaking. Controlled vocabularies are useful to point, but once you need to make graphs and inferences, they have no value compared to an ontology.

The challenges around documentation apply to **research software and code** as well as to research data. Participants remarked that **in a computing degree program, you learn how to document your code** and test it, and you gain other software engineering skills and habits. In contrast, scientists who use or develop research software are often self-taught or peer-taught; as a result, **scientists lack the skills and habits around properly documenting their process and outputs to make them reproducible**. One participant expressed it this way: the physical sciences community needs help in understanding the minimal information they need to generate to make code reproducible, and ideally the tools to make the task easier.

One participant also cautioned to be careful and **not assume that everyone knows what FAIR means**—they may not. Continued education and outreach are needed, especially to reach the new trainees and early-career researchers entering the field.

The comparison between research data and research software was echoed in the comments about **standards**. Some fields have community-agreed standards, others lack them. Software might be ahead of research in that respect. The standards are set by the community and generally adhered to; the standards are also accompanied by guidance on sharing, reuse, and collaboration. In research, the approach is more individualistic.

In the absence of accepted standards, **research data is shared at “a broad range of curation levels, from well-managed GitHub repositories to PDFs just shared to tick the box.”** There is lack of awareness and understanding of what needs to be recorded and shared.

Repositories vary in their structures and requirements as well, making it difficult and time-consuming to prepare the data for each one. Consistency would make the work easier.

The cost of data management and curation that enable data sharing is a barrier as well. These costs may not be covered by research grants or, if covered, the compliance is not monitored by the funders. In the time of a tight research funding and an intense competition to produce and publish results, these may be very real disincentives to data sharing.

The participants also commented on **the importance of a peer review of research data before the data is shared (or published)**, in parallel to the peer review of research papers. They expressed a desire for such

peer review, because it's one way **to verify data quality**. However, the availability of peer reviewers is a challenge even for standard research manuscripts submitted to journals for publication, and it is extremely limited for research data and research software that accompanies the manuscripts. For this reason, the quality of data and software associated with scientific papers often goes unchecked. There is also time pressure to “sign things off” and move the submission through the process to publication, which makes the peer review of data and software even less likely.

Still on the theme of data quality and the desirability of verifying such data quality before sharing (or publishing) the data, the participants commented on the **potential role of academic libraries and research services** at their institutions in that task. Currently this role is limited to only the technical aspects of the data, rather than a broader definition of quality. For instance, the **institutional repository** may check the raw data files to make sure they are not corrupt, but further examination of quality is difficult without understanding the research methodology, aims, and context.

External peer review—or “a pre-publish check for data”—would be ideal. But if not available, a **checklist for reviewing data** would be useful as well.

In addition, **data stewards may face a similar challenge when trying to evaluate research software** that goes with research data—without specialized knowledge, they may not be able to check if the software works as describes or how useful it is to the field.

Finally, on a basic technical level, **differences in file formats and software versions** (including between different operating systems) can be an issue even when sharing data with collaborators during the projects.

Digital notebooks and record keeping more generally were also mentioned. Researchers often lack training on responsible maintenance of notebooks. Some are more conscientious than others. They might write down what they plan to do but never update the information with what they actually did. Training, practical guidance, and perhaps even personal oversight (at least early on in their career) might be beneficial. So could be examples of good practice.

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) also came up in the discussion—both as a challenge and a possible solution. For instance, how do you manage **DOIs for data that gets updated over time**? You can create DOIs for snapshots, but that's a lot of data to store. It might be better to do DOI queries, so that the original query with time bounding can be re-run for reproducibility. What about DOIs for notebooks, experiments, results?

Hosting some data types externally to an organization may also be difficult. **Some data may be physical rather than digital**. For instance, the participants mentioned persistent identifiers for samples (IGSN); such identifiers would allow different researchers to go back to the same exact sample and perform different analyses; a linkage of data would also be possible.

Overall, the participants regarded data sharing as difficult. As one remarked, “**data sharing needs to be easy.**” Another term used was “**frictionless datasets.**”

5 Available Data Support in Physical Sciences

Edinburgh Workshop

The participants agreed that **researchers are often not sure where to seek support and what kind of support they need**. Perhaps understandably, the discussion veered toward the desired forms of support rather than the current existing ones.

Providing support at the point of need emerged as an important goal. Helping the users where and when they need help, often in very specific and practical ways. This could take the form of snippets and explainers, or sign posting to relevant and up-to-date resources. Webinars and podcasts may be useful too—taking advantage of the community knowledge and facilitating exchange of that knowledge.

For instance, **data lifecycle** could be used as a pointer to “when” a resource is useful, while **file formats** could be used as pointers for “where” to deposit the data (suggested repository locations). More long term, **AI could potentially assist** with the search and delivery of relevant information at the point of need.

Data exemplars were also mentioned. Researchers could learn from examples of good practice in the community (and also contribute such examples themselves). **Stories—or case studies—**around the technologies in different domains might also be a valuable learning resource.

Research training is needed but it’s a huge undertaking. Lots of research training already exists, but it could be better connected and organized, better curated—including training for specific roles, specific stages of research projects, and even potentially specific projects (bespoke training). The points of access to the training matter as well. These could be doctoral training centres or research services in academic libraries. In other words: **research training needs to be made more FAIR**—findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

Training could also lead to **digital badges and micro credentials**, to help with incentives and recognition. Ideally, all the research training for a discipline would all be collected on one platform, together with links to other disciplinary knowledge, reference materials, relevant laws and regulations, etc. The training could include self-paced courses as well as train-the-trainer packages that others could reuse to run their own training events.

In addition to training, **mentoring** could be very beneficial. Institutions and community organizations could consider offering a **formal mentoring service**, in which senior researchers in the community would give up some time to support early-career researchers. A similar mentoring service could be offered for data librarians or data stewards. Names like “Rent a mentor” and “Rent a data steward” were proposed here.

Incentives and rewards in the context of career paths were also discussed. Often the focus is on researchers, who already may have a clear career path to follow, with incentives and rewards along the way to encourage continued growth and excellence. It is important to **create similar career path and similar incentive and reward mechanisms for research/data support roles**: data stewards, data librarians, and similar. The first step might be to showcase the work of data stewards, not just researchers, on institutional websites and during events. Offer career guidance for research/data support roles. Stress the collaborative aspects of the research.

Another valuable form of support would be to create **funded fellowships for the development of specific outputs**.

More generally, the participants commented that **funders** are motivators for data sharing, but they often don’t offer support. The funding requirements can also be very general or flexible. More specific requirements might be better—they would encourage best practices or at least more consistent efforts around data sharing.

Participants also remarked that **costing services** (e.g., repositories for big data) is a challenge.

Southampton Workshop

As in the Edinburgh workshop, the discussion included both the existing forms of support and the desired ones.

In some cases, **researchers may not be aware of the available resources and support at their institution.** For instance, they may not realize that their institution has an institutional data repository.

The participants recognized **the role of academic libraries** in providing research & data support. Currently, such support services might offer generic advice—but the researchers need **domain-specific and practical advice**. Similarly, very generic templates (e.g., data management plans) may not be very useful; instead, **templates customized to the funder requirements** would have more value. On the other hand, the libraries can be a rich source of support because they have **rules and expertise to achieve a level of curation that helps reusability** of the data. For instance, they may require that specific conditions are fulfilled (e.g. recommended file formats) and the raw data is provided before they assign a DOI.

There was also a recognition that **data steward roles are very challenging**. Data stewards are often tasked with leading data sharing and similar work in their teams or at their institutions. They have to be very proactive and tell researchers what to do at every stage of the project; researchers are not coming and asking. This can be very time and labour intensive.

Institutional processes should better align with established best practices and conform to FAIR principles. For instance, facilities may identify data by institution and PI, not by DOI. The use of local identifiers instead of global persistent and unique identifiers is a barrier to data sharing.

Templates (e.g., for DMPs or for costing data management) are useful in helping researchers avoid duplicating efforts and reinventing the wheel, but the existing templates in physical sciences are not very good or they are hard to find.

Training was also discussed. For instance, Principal Investigators (PIs), typically senior researchers, could benefit from training on how to supervise and mentor researchers in their teams. They could also advocate for training for their team, particularly in order to encourage the researchers to spend more time on documenting the research properly, rather than only rushing to get the data and publish the results. On the other hand, there may be resistance from PIs and from institutional leaders if data sharing is already occurring, because if it's already being done, it might be easy to conclude that it's done well. Lack of knowledge may prevent people from seeing gaps or room for improvement when it comes to data sharing and RDM practices more generally, consistent with the saying "I don't know what I don't know."

Training tailored to specific roles would also be beneficial, as would be short, practical resources such as **"In a Nutshell" guides** and **glossaries** (e.g., a glossary of FAIR standards). One purpose of these resources would be to reduce complexity and make the information more accessible.

Credit and recognition—particularly for research/data support staff—were another theme. DURA was mentioned as an example of credit for open research. Prizes for good data management might be an effective way to both reward best practices and raise awareness of them.

Another way to acknowledge the contributions of research/data support staff and raise awareness of such topics as RDM, data sharing, and open science is to capture the stories of these staff members. **"A day in the life of a data steward" story could highlight both the challenges encountered and the real-life solutions.** It could also educate the community about the work of data stewards and possibly even encourage people to enter the field and take on this role.

The participants also brought up the notion of **hot and cold data repositories**. Cold repositories contain published data (cold storage); hot repositories contain data that is accessible to researchers working on the project but not necessarily to the public. There is an easy conversion from hot to cold.

6 Role of PSDI in Addressing the Data Challenges and Gaps in Support in Physical Sciences

Edinburgh Workshop

The workshop participants had a lot of ideas and suggestions regarding the possible role of PSDI in addressing the data challenges and gaps in support.

PSDI could play a role in **defining, curating, and disseminating standards for physical sciences research**. Such standards are often lacking, resulting in inconsistent and ad hoc solutions and posing a serious challenge to collaboration and data sharing. Clear disciplinary standards would benefit the researchers, save time and effort, and help the field advance.

PSDI could also play a crucial role in **delivering or curating relevant, up-to-date training** for the users. There is a need for discipline-specific training for the physical sciences. Training for supervisors and PIs, so that they recognize the knowledge and skills gaps in their teams and guide their teams toward required training as well.

Ideally, the training would target the **attitudes as well as knowledge and skills**, and in that way help bring about a larger cultural change with respect to data sharing. For instance, attitudes toward creating and utilizing DMPs as research tools rather than only because they are required. Or attitudes toward sharing negative results or imperfect, incomplete datasets that can still be of value to the field. Projects that didn't work are important to share; if never shared, other teams can waste time and resources duplicating the failures. One participant used the term "domain of failed dreams." How do we encourage researchers to share their failures as well as successes?

The participants also expressed interest in webinars on and guidance from the Pathfinders. One participant also mentioned the Coalition for Networked Information (CNI) series of short videos that highlight specific projects or tools as a good model to follow (more information available on the CNI website: <https://www.cni.org/resources/pbvs>).

Overall, **PSDI could become a trustworthy provider (or curator) of training and guidance** in physical sciences. A one-stop hub for essential training on RDM, FAIR data (including metadata, PIDs, licensing), as well as specific tools. PSDI could offer a **PSDI stamp of approval** for the best resources by linking them to its platform. But perhaps most importantly, it could save researchers time in searching through the large number of available trainings but pointing them to the shorter, curated list.

As one participant put it: PSDI could also become "a platform with all the knowledge in the field—links to relevant training, to reference materials, to laws and regulations, etc."

Longer term, **generative AI** (trained on carefully curated training data/ knowledge base) could also be utilized to answer questions and provide guidance in natural language, with proper sources and with links to additional resources and tools. It would essentially serve as a one-on-one consultation accessible 24/7 and always up to date.

PSDI could also take a lead in **building a community of practice in physical sciences**. In addition to collaborations and data sharing on the platform, PSDI could organize events to bring the community

together, build trust, and exchange knowledge. These could be invited talks by researchers about the projects; demonstrations and technical updates from data stewards and other data support professionals; funder presentations; as well as community discussions and working sessions focused on specific issues.

Sustainability of data repositories and data sharing solutions was another concern, and PSDI could play a role in supporting such sustainability. This could start with collecting and examining analytics from the repositories and seeing the patterns of use. What can the analytics tell us about how researchers search for data, access and download data, upload data, add metadata and other documentation? More broadly, it is important to consider the continuity of care across the data lifecycle. In the words of one participant: “we can't just take people's data if we can't guarantee how long we can preserve it for.” Longevity of data repositories is as important as their trustworthiness.

Quality assurance was another theme in the discussions—and another area where PSDI could provide guidance if not the actual service. Because sharing data of poor quality carries a risk of reputational damage, researchers are keen on having access to some quality control. This could be peer review at the time of submission to journals or a service provided by data repositories; or, at the very least, a set of guidelines and checks that the researchers could apply to their own datasets.

One participant also shared this idea to promote PSDI: “**an information pack about PSDI** to share with research support staff at the universities so they know about it and the services available and can point researchers to PSDI resources that are relevant to them.” A similar information pack could be disseminated to the industry as well.

Southampton Workshop

As in Edinburgh, the Southampton workshop participants readily shared ideas and suggestions regarding the possible role of PSDI in addressing the data challenges and gaps in support with respect to data sharing. Many ideas and suggestions from the Edinburgh workshops were echoed here.

The general view was that **research data sharing is challenging – and PSDI could make it easier**. This could extend to research software and other research objects.

PSDI could be the source of standards and of practical guidance on how to follow them. Data sharing practices are often inconsistent. Many researchers are self-taught with respect to how to share their data, and as a result do not always follow good practices. Alternatively, PSDI could raise the visibility of helpful tools and resources such as existing ontologies and foster their use in the field.

For instance, **the concept of “frictionless datasets”** was brought up. The physical sciences community needs to work out what that concept means – and PSDI could help.

Some of that work could stem from **PSDI facilitating community discussions**. The recommendations that PSDI provides would reflect collaboration and consensus to move in the same direction. **A data steward network** centred around PSDI could be one outcome.

PSDI could also provide or curate **relevant training and resources for both researchers and data support staff**. This includes topics like FAIR and RDM, but also training and resources focused on attitudes around data sharing and the needed cultural change.

Some specific topics in which PSDI could provide standards and guidance: **process recording, sensors and use of live data, active DMPs** (updated through the life of the project).

Research software could be another important area for PSDI. This could be software developed on top of the instrument software, enabling groups to create and share their standards and templates. One

participant commented that “running on top of an infrastructure that already works well is safer than developing a thing from scratch.”

In addition to generic resources, PSDI could also provide **consultancy and bespoke solutions** based on past projects, tools, and technologies used. This includes **templates and examples/ case studies** from different domains, for different roles, for different levels of experience.

There was also interest in PSDI providing (or signposting to) **FAIR assessment tools**. This could include FAIR assessment of datasets, software, as well as other research outputs.

PSDI could lead or support **initiatives aimed at students and more advanced trainees**. For instance, encouraging students to share (or publish) their data could be both a great experience and a source of recognition before they have a chance to publish a paper. Such initiatives could also help with the cultural change around data sharing that is needed.

PSDI could also give out **PSDI badges for datasets, projects, people, and organizations**. The badges would be a mark of credibility or best practices.

In terms of the business model, **researchers could have access to PSDI services in return for sharing their data on the platform** (or contributing in some other way).

The participants also agreed that PSDI could have a role in piloting and guiding **the responsible and effective use of AI in data management**. Ideas on AI tools that PSDI could trial included: help with guidance/ advice service; a simple validation tool to check the raw data files as well as metadata received by a repository; a DMP-building tool.

Finally, participants expressed **interest in learning more about PSDI and how to use it**. PSDI could also encourage the use of their platform and services by sharing case studies and lessons learned. How did other researchers use PSDI, from searching for datasets to final outcomes? Could the steps be shared and reused by others in the community?

7 Conclusion and Recommendations

The workshop participants voiced many current challenges to data sharing in physical sciences, from specific technical challenges to broad cultural challenges. These challenges—including a multitude of disconnected tools and processes, knowledge and support gaps, lack of community standards, and lack of community forum for discussion and collaboration—all present ripe opportunities for PSDI to bring value and help advance physical sciences to a fully digitally enabled and more integrated research discipline. The workshop discussions also highlighted a range of potential roles that PSDI could play in strengthening and advancing physical sciences research.

The two main recommendations from the workshops are as follows:

Recommendation 1: An integrated PSDI platform for data collection, storage, analysis, aggregation, and curation would help solve many technical problems and help establish and implement much needed standards and best practices in physical sciences research, while putting data sharing and open collaboration at the centre.

- Eliminate pain points to move the field toward “frictionless” data workflows.
- Standards and guidance on data management, data sharing, and documentation.
- At-the-point-of-need support as well as consultancy and bespoke solutions.
- Pilot and guide the responsible use of AI in physical sciences research.

Recommendation 2: In addition to providing an integrated technical solution, the PSDI platform could become a one-stop hub of up-to-date disciplinary knowledge, training, resources, and tools, as well as a community-building hub in physical sciences.

- A trusted provider and curator of online and in-person training.
- A community hub to foster trust, collaboration, and knowledge exchange.
- Funded fellowship for trainees and grants to develop specific outputs.

Future work could extend this report to specific subfields and specific roles in physical sciences research while also drilling down into the PSDI focus areas and emerging trends.

8 Appendix: Overview of the DCC

The Digital Curation Centre (DCC; <https://dcc.ac.uk/>), based at The University of Edinburgh and University of Glasgow, is a world-leading centre of expertise in digital information curation with a focus on building capacity, capability, and skills for research data management and data sharing. In addition to developing tools, resources, policies, and training on a range of data-related topics, the DCC team brings expertise and experience in facilitating collaborations, community building, and knowledge exchange, including through an annual International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC).